

D1.1. Management Guide and Collaboration Infrastructure

E. Kaldoudi [ATHENA]

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About ThrombUS+

Deep vein thrombosis (DVT) is the formation of a blood clot within the deep veins, most commonly those of the lower limbs, causing obstruction of blood flow. In 50% of people with DVT, the clot eventually breaks off and travels to the lung to cause pulmonary embolism. Clinical assessment of DVT is notoriously unreliable because up to 2/3 of DVT episodes are clinically silent and patients are symptom free even when pulmonary embolism has developed. Early diagnosis of DVT is crucial and despite the progress made in ultrasound imaging and plethysmography techniques, there is a need for new methods to enable continuous monitoring DVT diagnosis at the point of care.

ThrombUS+ brings together an interdisciplinary team of industrial, technology, regulatory, social science and clinical trial experts to develop a novel wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, operator free, continuous monitoring in patients with high DVT risk. The device will combine autonomous, AI driven DVT detection based on a novel wearable ultrasound hardware, impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography for immediate detection of blood clot formation in the lower limb. Activity and other physiological measurements will be used to provide a continuous assessment of DVT risk and support DVT prevention via serious gaming. The aggregated data will drive an intelligence decision support unit that will provide accurate monitoring and alerts. Extended reality will be used to guide experts to design exercises and patients to use the device optimally.

ThrombUS+ is intended for use by postoperative patients in the ward, during long surgical operations, cancer patients or otherwise bedridden patients at home or in care units, and women during pregnancy and postpartum. ThrombUS+ will use big data sets for AI training collected in the project via 3 large scale clinical studies and will validate the outcome in the clinical setting via 1 early feasibility study and 1 multi-center clinical trial.

Deliverable D1.1 Description

Management guide & collaboration infrastructure. The deliverable also includes a report detailing the project management guide and the private collaboration infrastructure. The collaboration infrastructure is private to the project team members. The management guide, to be distributed to all partners and team members and delivered to EU. This is the output of Task 1.1.

Terms and Definitions

Term	Definition
DESCA	Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EEA	Ethics External Advisor
EU	European Union
EUPATI	European Patients' Academy on Therapeutic Innovation
GA	General Assembly (when within the context of project management procedure)
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
MS	Microsoft®
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
PERT	Program Evaluation and Review Technique
PM	Project Manager
RP	Reporting Period
SAB	Stakeholders Advisory Board
TL	Task Leader
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive Summary

The aim of the ThrombUS+ Project Management Guide and Collaboration Infrastructure deliverable is to give a quick overview of the most relevant managerial aspects of the project, setting the rules and responsibilities of the partners aimed at ensuring a good quality and progress of the work.

This document will be updated when necessary, through duration of the project extending the information given, including relevant issues and changes in the project or procedures. Each time the document is updated, all partners will be duly informed about the updates and the changes made with respect to the previous version.

In the event of discrepancy between documents, this Deliverable is overruled by Grant Agreement including its Annexes and the Consortium Agreement with its possible addendums.

This document is a publishable summary of the deliverable.

1. ThrombUS+ at a Glance

1.1. Project Basis

1.1.1. Grant Agreement

The Grant Agreement is the contract concluded between the European Commission via European Health and Digital Executive Agency (representing the European Union) and the beneficiary (or beneficiaries) under which the parties receive the rights and obligations (e.g. the right of the Union's financial contribution and the obligation to carry out the research and development work).

Granting Authority or Funding Authority is the body awarding the grant for the project, in this case the European Commission via its executive agency HADEA (European Health and Digital Executive Agency).

ThrombUS+ Grant Agreement, no. 101137227, is available to all partners via the EC Sygma portal (<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/home>) and also via the internal project collaboration platform (see below). The Grant Agreement contains the following documents:

- The core document, which describes the terms and conditions
- Annex 1: Description of the action (Part A), which contains the list of participants, work packages, deliverables, milestones, critical risks and staff effort
- Annex 2: Description of the action (Part B), which contains the rest of the proposal document, including Sections on Excellence, Impact, Implementation and Clinical Studies
- Annex 2a: Additional information on unit costs and contributions
- Annex 3: Accession forms
- Annex 4: Model for the financial forms
- Annex 5: Specific rules

1.1.2. Consortium Agreement

The Consortium Agreement is an internal agreement which regulates the relations between consortium partners. This agreement does not involve the European Commission. It specifies binding commitments among the partners in addition to provisions of the Grant Agreement, definitions, description of the work to be done as well as technical, managerial, financial, and legal provisions.

The ThrombUS+ Consortium Agreement, developed based on the DESCA v03 model and signed by all partners on 1 November 2023, is available to all partners via the internal project collaboration platform (see below).

1.1.3. Project structure, duration and reporting periods

ThrombUS+ duration is 42 months, starting on 1 January 2024.

Project work is organized into 9 work packages (WP), each one comprising of several tasks and resulting in a number of deliverables. The guiding point of all work and planning will be the Deliverables and Milestones due to the Commission along the 3 reporting periods (RP) of ThrombUS+:

RP1: from month 1 to month 18

RP2: from month 19 to month 36

RP3: from month 37 to month 42

Annex 1 presents the project calendar, lists of WPs, tasks, deliverables, milestones and critical risks.

2. Project Management

2.1. Project Governance Structure

As outlined in Article 6 of the Consortium Agreement signed by ThrombUS+ partners on 1st November 2023, the internal organization of the Consortium is structured as follows:

The **Coordinator** is the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the Parties and the Granting Authority. The Coordinator shall, in addition to its responsibilities as a Party, perform the tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.

The **General Assembly (GA)** is the decision-making body of the consortium. The General Assembly consists of one representative of each Party (hereinafter referred to as “Member”). Each Member shall be deemed to be duly authorised to deliberate, negotiate and decide on all matters discussed in the General Assembly. The Coordinator shall chair all meetings of the General Assembly, unless decided otherwise by the General Assembly.

ThrombUS+ **General Assembly consists of 18 members.**

Quorum is reached when 2/3 of the members are present, i.e. 12 members (Consortium Agreement, 6.3.4.1.)

Decisions are taken by a majority of 2/3 of the votes cast (Consortium Agreement, 6.3.4.4).

2.2. Project Management Structure

ThrombUS+ project management structure is summarized in Figure 1.

Decision making management is performed by project governance structure as described above and detailed in Article 6 of the Consortium Agreement.

Strategic management is performed by the Coordinator and the General Assembly via the procedures of the project governance, and supported by the Ethics External Advisor (EEA) and an Stakeholders Advisory Board (SAB) appointed by the GA.

The **Ethics External Advisor (EEA)**, as requested by EC, has expertise in human-centred technology (AI-powered technology in particular), to help prioritise the well-being of the participants in the clinical trials and studies, and help the project adopt an ethics-by-design approach. A report by the ethics advisor must be submitted to cover these issues every year starting at M12.

The **Stakeholder Advisory Board (SAB)** comprises of leading experts in the fields ThrombUS+ innovation. They will provide comments and scientific/technical advice according to their expertise, as well as feedback on major project technical decisions and deliverables. The members of the SAB will offer their services free of charge and may be asked to review key deliverables and participate in project meetings. The members of the SAB shall sign nondisclosure agreements with the Coordinator before engaging with the project.

The Project Coordinator and General Assembly is supported by the **Project Manager (PM)**. The PM undertakes the project financial management, reporting, organization of project meetings and in general the project administrative support and is overall responsible for the logistics and quality assurance of the project management.

Operational management is performed by the Work Package Leaders (WPL) in close collaboration with the Coordinator and GA.

The **Work Package Leaders (WPL)** have the overall responsibility for the progress and results of each respective work package, while specific responsibilities include: propose and implement a detailed plan for the work package (WP); coordinate technical and scientific work in line with the overall project work plan; coordinate the development and delivery of the WP deliverables, and monitor the respective quality control

procedures; to organize WP meetings and provide other communication mechanisms as needed to ensure the quality of the WP results; to establish and coordinate joint work and planning with related work packages, and to manage the exchange of information where necessary.

Implementation is managed by Task Leaders (TLs). Task Leaders will be responsible to elaborate the work under their tasks and coordinate the members involved. Each Task in individual WPs is led by a consortium member who nominates a Task Leader (TL).

Task Team members are responsible for the elaboration and on time delivery of the work package’s deliverables and results. They work under direct control of their respective WP/Task Leader and report directly to them. The task teams will set up coordination sessions during consortium meetings but will also use frequently other communication channels like teleconference calls.

Figure 1. Project management structure.

2.3. Persons Appointed

2.3.1. Project Coordinator

ATHENA: Prof. Eleni Kaldoudi [F]

2.3.2. Project Manager

ATHENA: Dr. Stylianos (Stelios) Didaskalou [M]

2.3.3. General Assembly Members

No	Partner	GA Representative	F/M	Email
1	ATHENA	Prof. Eleni Kaldoudi	F	kaldoudi@athenarc.gr
2	KTU	Prof. Vaidotas Marozas	M	vaidotas.marozas@ktu.lt
3	VERMON	Dr. Mathieu Legros	M	m.legros@vermon.com
4	FRAUNHOFER	Mr. Marco Kircher	M	Marco.kircher@ipms.fraunhofer.de
5	TELEMED	Mr. Dmitry Novikov	M	d.novikov@pcultrasound.com
6	EchoNous	Mr. Pavlos Moustakidis	M	pavlos.moustakidis@echonous.com
7	MEDIS	Mrs. Susann Balling	F	sb@medis.company
8	ComfTech	Mrs. Lara Alessia Moltani	F	alessia.moltani@comfttech.com
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13	HSV	Dr. Maxime Gautier	M	maxime.gautier@ch-simoneveil.fr
14	VDE	Dr. Thorsten Prinz	M	thorsten.prinz@vde.com
15	MEDEA	Mr. Pietro Dionisio	M	p.dionisio@medeaproject.eu
16	PHAZE	Mr. Spyridon Anagnostopoulos	M	spiros.anagnostopoulos@phazeclinical.com
17	PBY	Dr. Frans Folkvord	M	ffolkvord@predictby.com
18	SciGen	Ms. Eleni Briola	F	eleni.briola@scigentech.com

2.3.4. Work Package and Task Leaders

Work package or task		Partner	Lead person	F/M
WP1	Project Management	ATHENA	Eleni Kaldoudi	F
T1.1	Project communication and coordination	ATHENA	Eleni Kaldoudi	F
T1.2	Administrative and financial management	ATHENA	Eleni Kaldoudi	F
T1.3	Quality assurance and risk management	ATHENA	Stelios Didaskalou	M
T1.4	Innovation IPR management	MEDEA	Pietro Dionisio	M
T1.5	Open science and open data management plan	ATHENA	Stelios Didaskalou	M
WP2	Requirements and product co-design	PBY	Lucas Javier Segal	M
T2.1	Patient-centric cases and requirements definition	PBY	Lucas Javier Segal	M
T2.2	Regulatory framework, security, safety and ethics	VDE	Thorsten Prinz	M
T2.3	Technical and functional requirements	KTU	Vaidotas Marozas	M
T2.4	Co-creation of architectural design	ComfTech	Lara Alessia Moltani	F
WP3	Wearable ultrasound device	TELEMED	Dmitry Novikov	M
T3.1	Transducer – bulk technology	VERMON	Mathieu Legros	M
T3.2	Transducer – MEMS technology	FRAUNHOFER	Marco Kircher	M
T3.3	Precise tissue compression actuator	KTU	Saulius Daukantas	M
T3.4	Ultrasound transducer control and image formation	TELEMED	Andrius Sakalauskas	M
T3.5	Testing, image quality and performance enhancements	TELEMED	Andrius Sakalauskas	M
T3.6	Integration, assembly & characterization in a final probe	KTU	Rytis Jurkonis	M
WP4	Wearable sensor network	ComfTech	Lara Alessia Moltani	F
T4.1	Impedance plethysmography spectroscopy hardware	TAU	Antti Vehkaoja	M
T4.2	Light reflection rheography hardware	MEDIS	Jürgen Querengässer	M
T4.3	Lower limb activity sensor network	KTU	Mantas Jucevičius	M
T4.4	Wearable development and integration with sensors	ComfTech	Lara Alessia Moltani	F
T4.5	Testing, signal quality, performance enhancements	KTU	Mantas Jucevičius	M
T4.6	Manufacturing of prototypes	ComfTech	Lara Alessia Moltani	F
WP5	DVT risk estimation, detection & prevention	ATHENA	George Drosatos	M
T5.1	DVT detection based on wearable ultrasound	EchoNous	Mattheu Cook	M
T5.2	DVT detection by impedance & light plethysmography	TAU	Antti Vehkaoja	M
T5.3	Personalized DVT risk estimation	ATHENA	Aliko Fiska	F
T5.4	Serious game for DVT risk prevention	ATHENA	Chari Kiourt	M
T5.5	Extended reality for operator/user guidance	ATHENA	Kosmas Kritsis	M

Work package or task		Partner	Lead person	F/M
WP6	Integration and validation	KTU	Vaidotas Marozas	M
T6.1	Product design specifications	KTU	Vaidotas Marozas	M
T6.2	Testing methodology and test plan	KTU	Andrius Rapalis	M
T6.3	Hardware integration and testing	KTU	Saulius Daukantas	M
T6.4	Software integration and app	ATHENA	George Drosatos	M
T6.5	Hardware and software integration	KTU	Saulius Daukantas	M
WP7	Clinical studies	PHAZE	Ioanna Drougka	F
T7.1	Clinical studies initiation	PHAZE	Ioanna Drougka	F
T7.2	Study A	PHAZE	Ioanna Drougka	F
T7.3	Studies B1 and B2	PHAZE	Ioanna Drougka	F
T7.4	Studies C1 and C2	PHAZE	Ioanna Drougka	F
T7.5	Posting of results of clinical trials	PHAZE	Ioanna Drougka	F
WP8	Communication and dissemination	SciGen	Eleni Briola	F
T8.1	Communication and dissemination plan and activities	SciGen	Eleni Briola	F
T8.2	Publishing the data set of Clinical Study A	ATHENA	Stelios Didaskalou	M
T8.3	Organization of a data challenge	SciGen	Eleni Briola	F
T8.4	Stakeholder engagement and clustering	SciGen	Eleni Briola	F
T8.5	Creating awareness on gender balance	ATHENA	Eleni Kaldoudi	F
WP9	Exploitation and commercialization	MEDEA	Pietro Dionisio	M
T9.1	Regulatory compliance monitoring and mitigation	VDE	Thorsten Prinz	M
T9.2	Cost-effective analysis and business model	PBY	Frans Folkvord	M
T9.3	Preparation for next phase clinical trials	PHAZE	Ioanna Drougka	F
T9.4	Exploitation plan, commercialization strategy	MEDEA	Pietro Dionisio	M

2.3.5. Stakeholder Advisory Board

1. **Nicola Merlin**, EUPATI Expert Patient, President of the Italian EUPATI network, Italy

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/nicola-merlin-641632183/>

Established lawyer, national president of the Feder-AIPA ODV association since 2015 and member of the Italian Stroke Observatory. Active in the Third Sector for more than twenty years. Patient Advocacy Manager. EUPATI Expert Patient in drug research and development. Since 2019 he has been part of the Academia de Paziente Esperto EUPATI Conoscere per Decidere (<https://accademiadeipazienti.org/>) and since the end of November 2022 he is its President.

2. **Panos Athanasiou** – General Manager, Adelco SA Pharmaceuticals and Cosmetics Industry, Greece

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/panosathanasiou/?originalSubdomain=gr>

Panos Athanasiou is the General Manager in the pharmaceutical company Adelco SA and Managing Director of the Australian subsidiary Adelco Pharmaceuticals Australia Pty Ltd. He was born in Chania, Crete, in 1972. He holds a degree in Medical Laboratories from West Attica University Health and Welfare Sciences, and a bachelor's and master's degree in business administration from British Hellenic College and the University of Wales. He started his career in Petrola SA and Shell SA (1994-1997), petroleum and chemical companies in their export departments, and then specialized in pharmaceutical marketing and sales of Greek pharmaceutical products in the global market. He joined Adelco SA (1998-2006) as an executive, initially as Export Manager, and then as Commercial Director. Following step, he was recruited as General Manager of Remedy Ltd in a joint venture with Hygeia group to create Y-pharma (2007). In his next role, he was appointed in Genepharm SA as Distribution Management Director ROW (2007-2008). In the end of 2008, he founded Eris Pharmaceuticals Australia Ltd (2008-2016), based in Melbourne/Australia, where he was CEO, a new and innovative pharmaceutical entity with offices in Melbourne AU, Athens GR and Amman JO, creating a portfolio of 220 branded medicines, acquiring Aurobindo Australia Ltd in 2015 and achieving active presence and registrations/sales in 25 countries. With the successful sale of Eris Pharma to new shareholders (2016), he returned to Greece, and to the company where he began his career in in the pharmaceutical field, Adelco SA, where in close collaboration with the ownership, he serves as General Manager (end of 2016) in the Greek entity and MD of the Australian subsidiary Adelco Pharmaceuticals Australia Pty Ltd. He has contributed as an executive pharma consultant to various working groups of industry associations (PSVAK, HEPO, etc.), and institutional bodies in Greece and Australia and in many R&D projects in the pharmaceutical field.

3. **Dominique Certon**, Professor in Electrical Engineering Systems, University of Tours, France

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/dominique-certon-2853674/>

Dominique Certon received an M.Sc. degree in signal processing and electrical engineering in 1991 from the University of Orléans, France. In 1994, he received a Ph.D. degree from the University of Tours, France. Finally, he obtained his Habilitation à Diriger les Recherches (HDR) in applied acoustics and materials engineering from the University of Tours in 2006. He is a full professor in Electrical Engineering Systems at the Polytech Tours Engineering School. In addition to his research activities, he is currently in charge of coordinating the Electronics & Energy Department. His research activities focus on ultrasonic probes and related instrumentation applied to medical imaging, non destructive testing and metrology. From more than ten years ago, he developed strong know-how in the design, modelling and characterization of MEMS-based ultrasonic transducer, i.e. Capacitive Micromachined Ultrasonic Transducers (CMUT). He also has over ten years of research experience with multi-element probes based on piezoelectric materials, and more specifically with piezo-composite materials. He has been involved in several national and international research projects (30) and has coordinated national research

projects funded by the French National Research Agency. A large part of its activities has led to strong industrial collaborations and the transfer of know-how. This relationship with industry has enabled the development of tools for modeling multi-element ultrasound probes that are now used and exploited by some of its industrial partners. He is author or coauthor of more than 60 communications and publications. He is a member of the French Society of Acoustics and IEEE society. He is member of the Editorial Board of the Ultrasonics open access journal by Elsevier (Citescor: 7.5, IF: 4.2).

4. **Niko Pagoulatos**, PhD, Medical Technology Executive, USA

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/niko-pagoulatos/>

Niko Pagoulatos, Ph.D. is a technology executive and innovator with 25+ years of experience in engineering, clinical and business aspects of specialized medical ultrasound imaging. Dr. Pagoulatos earned his B.S. in Physics from the University of Athens in Greece and completed his graduate studies at the University of Washington in Seattle, where he earned a M.S. in Bioengineering in addition to a M.S. and Ph.D. in Electrical Engineering. Prior to joining Spectral AI, Dr. Pagoulatos held multiple executive roles at EchoNous, a global healthcare AI-focused medical ultrasound innovation company. Prior to EchoNous, Dr. Pagoulatos held director and advanced research and development engineering roles at FUJIFILM SonoSite, the world leader in point-of-care ultrasound, DYSIS Medical, a company focused on early detection and diagnosis of cervical disease using biophotonics, and Siemens Healthcare. Dr. Pagoulatos is the inventor of the breakthrough enhanced needle visualization technology in point-of-care ultrasound, which has become a standard imaging mode in point-of-care ultrasound globally, allowing physicians to visualize needles significantly better than standard ultrasound imaging during ultrasound-guided needle procedures. Built and led a team that developed a groundbreaking innovative handheld ultrasound system, Kosmos (EchoNous Inc), with several key industry-first technologies and features: (i) first ever handheld ultrasound imaging system with continuous wave doppler allowing for quantification of valve disease, (ii) automated AI guidance for cardiac imaging (primary inventor of granted patent) accelerating learning curve for new ultrasound users, and (iii) first ever and only fully-integrated auscultation and ECG capability into the ultrasound probe (primary inventor of granted patent), ideal for medical education and training, and with the potential to drive new clinical protocols for improved diagnostic capability at the point of care.

5. **Pantelis Natsiavas**, PhD, Researcher, Institute of Applied Biosciences at the Centre for Research and Technology Hellas

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/pantelis-natsiavas-52a30723/>

Dr. Pantelis Natsiavas is a Researcher (Grade C) at the Institute of Applied Biosciences of Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (INAB|CERTH), heading the eHealth Lab in Thessaloniki, Greece. He holds a PhD from Sorbonne University (Paris, France) and two MSc degrees and a Diploma of Electrical and Computer Engineering from the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH). He has received a scholarship from the French Government and has been a visitor researcher for the LIMICS lab (Paris, France), while he has also worked as a Software Engineer with companies both located in Greece and abroad, providing services regarding software development and consulting for more than 10 years. Since 2013, he has been part of many European and national R&D projects on Medical Informatics, related with telemonitoring, health data security, drug safety and pharmacovigilance, focusing on the use of Knowledge Engineering approaches (e.g. the creation and use of ontological models and knowledge graphs). Currently, he is the Technical Coordinator of MyPal project (Horizon 2020 framework) and the “Hellenic registry of patients with chronic respiratory conditions and home mechanical ventilation support”, maintaining clinical data from 11 disparities across Greece. Finally, he is the Principal Investigator for the project PVClinical and the main contact for the OHDSI network’s National Node for Greece, on behalf of INAB|CERTH.

3. Project Internal Communication

3.1. Basic Communication

Basic communication within the consortium is based on email.

A number of different contact lists have been compiled and will be updated and maintained during the course of the project. These contact lists are available to all consortium team members via the internal project file sharing infrastructure. Also, basic contact information of the Coordinator and Project Manager, as well as of all Team Leaders and WP Leaders is available on the public project web site (under “contact”).

Main contact lists maintained include information for:

- EC project officers: this is to be used only by the Coordinator;
- Coordinating Partner: this includes contact details for the Coordinator, Project Manager, Chief Administrative Person for the Coordinating Partner and Legal Representative;
- General Assembly members;
- WP Leaders;
- Task Leaders for each WP;
- Team members for each partner; and
- Team members of the entire consortium.

The project mailing contact lists as of today are provided in Annex 1 to this deliverable. Annex 1 is continually updated and provided to the consortium partners via the internal project file sharing infrastructure.

3.2. Virtual Meetings

Virtual consortium meetings will be held routinely in addition to the scheduled Project Consortium Meetings. These virtual meetings will mainly be called for discussing and resolving specific issues within rather small groups. Examples of such situations where a virtual meeting may be called are:

- regular GA meetings, when these do not coincide with an actual project consortium meeting;
- technical discussions of working teams of a certain Task of WP;
- bilateral technical meetings;
- review meetings for deliverables;

The basic tool for administering virtual meetings the MS Teams platform maintained by ATHENA.

Other similar platforms may be used, especially when considering bilateral or small group meetings organized by individual WP or Task leaders.

3.3. Event Scheduling

Event scheduling is facilitated using Doodle, a free web-based event scheduler (available at <http://doodle.com/>). All planned events (e.g. real meetings, virtual meetings, review meetings, clustering or dissemination events, etc.) are recorded in the project’s internal event calendar on the internal collaboration infrastructure.

3.4. Collaboration Infrastructure

The main project collaboration infrastructure is MS Teams maintained and provided for the Consortium by ATHENA. A ThrombUS+ team has been set in the ATHENA MS Teams/SharePoint platform and all ThrombUS+ team members are invited to join.

The team exhibits various collaboration channels, for administration and for each respective work package and meetings. Each channel allows for synchronous team videoconferencing, team instant messaging, and file sharing, while several respective Teams tools are available for use. Figure 2 shows a screenshot of the project collaboration infrastructure.

Figure 2. Screenshot of the ThrombUS+ team collaboration infrastructure.

3.5. Document Exchange and Archive

Simple document exchange for everyday work may be performed via email. However, major project documents are exchanged, co-edited and archived via MS Teams maintained and provided for the Consortium by ATHENA.

Also, the General Channel in the ThrombUS+ team exhibits a document folder structure dedicated to finalized versions of all project documents and other support documents, e.g. This document library is dynamic and will be updated continuously during the project duration as the need arises.

Figure 3 shows screenshots of the document folder structure in MS SharePoint, also accessible via the Teams collaboration infrastructure, which at project kick-off exhibits the following main structure:

1. **General Project Documents:** reserved for project contractual documents, Horizon program guides, project templates and dissemination material. At this stage, it contains the following areas:
 - Call Documents: include work program and proposal
 - Grant Agreement
 - Consortium Agreement
 - Other Agreements (e.g. NDA)
 - Horizon support files: including financial guides and any other EC prepared guiding documents
 - Project at a Glance: DoA .docx file, and supporting PowerPoint and excel documents (Gantt diagram, budget, deliverables, milestones, risks, etc.)

- Templates: including deliverable templates, meeting agenda/minutes templates, presentation templates, etc.
 - Dissemination Materials: intended for project dissemination materials, e.g. leaflets, project presentation, videos, etc.
2. **Meetings:** reserved for all documents that relate to the organization and the workings of various types of project meetings, including attendance lists, final agendas and minutes. At this stage the following main categories of meetings have been pre-arranged:
 - General Assemblies
 - Project Consortium Meetings
 - Review Meetings
 - Other technical and bilateral meetings
 3. **Deliverables:** reserved as an archive of final deliverable source files and the corresponding deliverable reviews. This area will also serve as a collective single folder for the Ethics External Advisor and the External Advisory Board to access project outcomes.
 4. **Publications:** Copies of project publications and presentations in conferences and other events.
 5. **Contact Lists:** reserved for the various project contact lists and their updates.

Figure 3. Screenshot of the document folder structure in MS SharePoint maintained and provided by ATHENA.

ANNEXES

- 1| Consortium
- 2| Project Calendar
- 3| Work Packages and Tasks
- 4| Deliverables
- 5| Milestones
- 6| Gantt Chart
- 7| PERT Chart
- 8| Critical Risks
- 9| Contacts